

After school, the necessary functional maturity is achieved, that is, "school adulthood". "I don't know," he said, " but I'm sure you're right." But when you reach adolescence, you will have to pay for the crisis of that age and the accompanying neurosis. One of the problems that make it difficult to master the curriculum is somatic weakness. Teacher V. A. Sukhomlinsky, paying attention to the intellectual development and health of students, said that "slow thinking is the result of general morbidity."

Although the basis of the activity of a teacher – psychologist in schools is a short list of activities and tasks that are based on the development of students' personality, it is proposed to use a typological method in the practice of pedagogical and psychological service in schools, as it learns the characteristics of tasks, difficulties, problems, methods and methods of their solution that are characteristic of the educational period. The typology proposed by US allows us to develop more generalized strategies of professional, pedagogical and socio - psychological work (with respect to each individual), which are carried out with different groups of students (typical on a certain basis).

Psychodiagnostic and design methods of research differ from the typology (Kettel. The proposed diagnosis may be related to the formation of professional training in a higher educational institution, professionally significant qualities, and plans for the future based on personal requirements. Typological diagnostics the ability to solve various tasks of Student Life is based on the method of progressive, that is, open typology, in which the strategies chosen by him in solving various contradictions are supplemented by new knowledge about the individual based on feedback about his ability to participate in Student Society. Typological diagnostics treat student age as an age of reflection –not only their own personal qualities, but also the recognition of those qualities that were used in professional situations in reality life. Therefore, it can exist as a method of self-awareness, which cannot be used by diagnostic methods that require other, more complex explanations.

The concept of individual organization of time can include in itself the results of the study of the time Order of activity in various professions (for example, the French psychologist Sh. Godbua studied the mode of Organization of time for nurses working on a two-shift work schedule for 20 years). Some of the time modes of activity that occur in various professions are mentioned: the most popular is the time deficit (its lack in the performance of activities) Limit Mode (where the subject must perform the work under certain pressure, expedited to complete the work on time), the mode in which the term of completion of the service is not specified (found in the creative professions of writers, artists, scientists), the Effective Time Mode in the implementation of the work (average standard), etc. in the course of studying how different subjects work in a certain mode of activity, it was found that the most important factor in the organization of a person's time is the transfer of time internally or externally.

References

1. Aldamuratov A. A. interesting psychology. Almaty, Kazakh University, 1991-112 P
2. Zharykbayev K. B. Psychology. "I'm sorry," he said. Almaty, "school", 1982
3. General Psychology. Edited by V. Bogoslovsky, A. A. Stepanov, A. G. Kovalev. 2nd edition translated into Kazakh. "No," she said.:1980
4. Zhusupbek A. Psychology. "No," she said.: 1995-310b.
5. Likhachevb.T. Pedagogikakurs lecture.Moscow, "Prometheus", 1992 s 330
- 6.

FEATURES OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ADOLESCENTS

Dzhamashova Gulnur Ablakhatovna

Master teacher of the department "Pedagogy" Shymkent University, Shymkent Kazakhstan

Abstract the desire of a teenager to be independent, to give birth under the care of adults is found in all children, and a number of them read fantastic literature day and night, imitating their characters.

During the extracurricular period, a teenager learns radio engineering and electrical engineering. "I don't